

AGIC 5

“Conference Program Book 5th Atlas Georesources International Congress”

Geosciences and Water Security Challenges under Climate Change

November 8-10, 2024

Hammamet, Tunisia

SCAN ME

1	WELCOME MESSAGE
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Dear Esteemed Guests, Colleagues and friends,

On behalf of the **AGIC5** Organizing committee, I am delighted to welcome you to the 5th Atlas Georesources International Congress (AGIC5) which held from 8th November to 10th November 2024 in Hammamet, Tunisia. This 5th Edition of AGIC focuses on serious water challenges facing Tunisia and Mediterrean region. It will cover a wide range of research fields of research from the resource exploration to the application of innovative technologies for monitoring and treatment.

Since its first edition in 2017, AGIC has become an important scientific event. This symposium provided an opportunity for water stakeholders including researchers, experts, Industrials, policymakers to exchange knowledge, share best practices and present the latest results related to water resources.

This edition of the conference has the overall theme "Geosciences and Water Security Challenges under Climate Change" and its main sub-themes of :

- Groundwater management and Surface water monitoring and Groundwater recharge
- Climate change and water
- Water treatment and reuse of non-conventional water
- Pollutant control and Water quality assessment
- GIS, Remote sensing, and IA applied to water resource
- Hydro-Hazards and Early warning system
- Geological Modeling and Resources Exploration

AGIC5 program included plenary sessions, followed by parallel sessions focused on the main sub-themes of congress. Special sessions will also bring together experts to discuss and find solutions to key water challenges facing society and the environment.

In addition, the poster sessions will offer students and young researchers the opportunity to present their latest findings. A student poster award will also be given to recognize outstanding research contributions.

Last but not least, I would like to express my gratitude to the four co-chairs for their excellent coordination. I also want to thank the volunteers from the organizing committee, the scientific coordinators and reviewers for their valuable work to select outstanding presentations. Finally, I would like also to thank all partners for their support.

Enjoy the AGIC5
Prof. Ammar MLAYAH
Water Research and Technologies Center (CERTE)
Chairman AGIC5

Water Research and Technologies Center, Borj Cedria (CERTE)

Laboratory of Georesources (LGR)

Tunisian Association of Georesources (ATGr)

Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research (MHESR)

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Sustainable water reuse practices improving safety in agriculture, food and environment – SAFE, PRIMA

Euro-Mediterranean Journal for Environmental Integration Journal (EMJEI), Springer Nature

Tunis International Center for Digital Cultural Economy

Geophysics and Geosciences Network (GGN)

Centre de Biotechnologie de Borj-Cédria

Société Tunisienne d'Electricité et de Gaz (STEG)

AGIC5

5th Atlas Georesources International Congress
Hammamet, Tunisia, November 8-10, 2024

Société Tunisienne de l'Electricité et du Gaz (STEG)

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Dr. Mohamed Dhaoui, CERTE
Dr. Mohamed Kefi, CERTE
Dr. Mourad El Koundi, EABA

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Dr. Imen Oueslati, CBBC
Dr. Mouez Gouasmia, FSGf

AGIC5 Sessions Coordinators

Groundwater management and surface water monitoring and Groundwater recharge		
Dr. Faten Jarraya- Horriche CERTE/IAH	Dr. Fayrouz Slama ENIT / IAH	Prof. Joanna Doummar American University of Beirut, Lebanon / IAH
Climate change and water		
Dr. Haykel Sallemi CERTE		
Water treatment and reuse of non-conventional water		
Prof. Marc Heran University of Montpellier, France	Dr. Feyda Srarfi FST, University El Manar	
Pollutant control and Water quality assessment		
Dr. Taissire Ben Amor CERTE	Dr. Kawther Ben Mabrouk CERTE	
GIS, Remote sensing, and IA applied to water resource		
Prof. Imed Riadh Farah MSE, University of Manouba	Dr. Mourad EL Koundi EABA	Dr. Ahmed Ezzine CNCT
Hydro-Hazards and Early warning system		
Mrs Thouraya Sahli Chahed CNCT		
Geological Modeling and Resources Exploration		
Prof. Hayet Chihi CERTE		

Special Sessions Coordinators

Treasure Network Event : REUSE opportunities through Treasure Network		
Prof. Jérôme Harmand, INRAE		
Geophysics and Geosciences Network (GGN) Event : 1 st Geosciences and Environment Interdisciplinary Meetings		
Dr. Mohamed Dhaoui CERTE	Dr. Mourad El Koundi EABA	
SAFE Event : Bridging the gap between science and society : Towards a sustainable water resources management in Cap Bon region, NE Tunisia		
Dr. Samia Khadhar CERTE	Dr. Anis Chkirbene INAT	Eng. Ali Ben Ammar CRDA Nabeul

Members / Reviewers

	Reviewer Name	Affiliation
Prof	Abdelaziz Mridekh	Université Ibn Tofail, Morocco
Dr	Abdelaziz Sbaai	FST, Université Tunis El Manar
Dr	Abdelhamid Ben Salem	ETAP
Dr	Adel Kharroubi	ISSTEGb, University of Gabes
Prof	Amina Mabrouk	FST, University Tunis El Manar
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Dr	Badra El Abed	CERTE
Dr	Belgacem Akoubi	ISSTEGb, University of Gabes
Dr	Chafai Azri	FSS, University of Sfax
Dr	Dat Pham	Macquarie University, Australia
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Dr	Fatma Trabelsi	ESIM
Dr	Feyda Srarfi	FST, University of Tunis El Manar
Dr	Habib Abida	FSS, University of Sfax
Prof	Hayet Chihi	CERTE
Dr	Haykel Sellami	CERTE
Dr	Houda Zendah	CERTE
Dr	Imen Dridi	FST, Université Tunis El Manar
Dr	Kawther Ben Mabrouk	CERTE
Dr	Lamine Hamai	CRAAG Alegria
Prof	Mabrouk Boughdiri	FSB, University of Carthage
Prof	Marc Heran	Montpellier University, France
Dr	Maroua Bouteffeha	LMHE - ENIT
Dr	Mohamed El Bouhaddioui	ENIM Morocco
Prof	Mohamed Gasmi	FSB, University of Carthage
Dr	Mohamed Gharbi	CERTE
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Dr	Nesrine Kalboussi	CERTE
Dr	Nesrine Kamoun	CERTE
Dr	Nesrine Nasri	ISTEUB/LMHE
Dr	Noureddien Hamdi	ISSTEGb, University of Gabes
Dr	Rachid Boukhchina	ISSTEGb, University of Gabes
Dr	Riahi Sami	FST, University of Tunis El Manar
Dr	Rim Ben Amor	FST, Université Tunis El Manar
Prof	Salem Bouri	FSS, University of Sfax
Dr	Samira Melki	CERTE
Dr	Sonia Gannouni	CERTE
Dr	Soumaya Hajji	FST, Université Tunis El Manar
Dr	Taissire Ben Amor	CERTE
Prof	Jérôme Harmand	INRAE, France
Dr	Yudi Setiawan	Center for Environmental Research, IPB University, Indonesia

Day 1 : Friday 8 November 2024				
13 : 00 – 14 : 00	Registration desk Open			
14:00 – 14 :30	Opening Ceremony Welcome Address by Conference Chairs Official Opening of AGIC5			
14:30 – 16:00	Plenary Lectures			
16:00 – 16:30	Break			
Parallel Sessions I				
16:30 – 18:00	Room 1	Room 2		
	SubS1 : Groundwater management and surface water monitoring and Groundwater Recharge	SubS1 : GIS, Remote sensing, and IA applied to water resource		
18:00-19:00	Workshop : How to write a Scientific paper ?			
Day 2 : Saturday 9 November 2024				
8:30 – 12:00	Registration desk Open			
8:30 – 9:30	Plenary Lectures			
Parallel Sessions II				
Time	Room 1	Room 2	Room 3	Room 4
9:30 – 11:00	SubS1 : Geological modeling for resources exploration	SubS1 : Pollutant control and Water quality assessment	GGN Event (I) 1 st Geosciences and Environment Interdisciplinary Meetings	SAFE Event (I) Bridging the gap between science and society
Parallel Sessions III				
Time	Room 1	Room 2	Room 3	Room 4
11:30 – 13:00	Climate change and water	Treasure Network Event REUSE opportunities through Treasure Network	GGN Event (II) 1 st Geosciences and Environment Interdisciplinary Meetings	SAFE Event (II) Bridging the gap between science and society
13:00- 14:00	Lunch			
Parallel Sessions IV				
Time	Room 1	Room 2	Room 3	
14:00 – 15:45	SubS2 : Geological modeling for resources exploration	Water treatment and reuse of non-conventional water	GGN Event (III) 1 st Geosciences and Environment Interdisciplinary Meetings	
15:45 – 16:15	Break + Poster viewing			
16:15 – 18:00	Room 1& Room 2		Room 3	
	Poster Contest / Lighting talk		GGN Event (IV) 1 st Geosciences and Environment Interdisciplinary Meetings	
Day 3 : Sunday 10 November 2024				
8:30 – 10:00	Registration desk Open			
8:30 – 9:30	Plenary Lectures			
Parallel Sessions V				
Time	Room 1	Room 2	Room 3	
9:30 – 11:00	SubS2 : Groundwater management and surface water monitoring and Groundwater Recharge	SubS2 : GIS, Remote sensing, and IA applied to water resource	SubS2 : Pollutant control and Water quality assessment	
11:00 – 11:30	Break			
11:30 – 13:00	Closing Ceremony Session reports by coordinators / Global Discussion / Poster Awards / Closing remarks			
13:00 – 14:30	Lunch			

Day 1 : Friday, November 8 th , 2024		
13:00 – 14:00	AGIC5 Registration Opening	
OPENING CEREMONY		
Masters of Ceremony : Dr. Mohamed Kefi & Dr. Samia Khadhar		
Venue : Room 1		
14:00 – 14:30	<p><i>Welcome Address</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prof. Ammar Mlayah, Chairman AGIC5, CERTE <p><i>Official Opening of AGIC5</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prof. Hakim Gabtni, General Director, CERTE - Representative from Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research (MHESR) - Representative from Ministry of Ministry of Agriculture, Hydraulic Resources and Fisheries 	
PLENARY LECTURES		
14:30 – 16:00	<p>Water Scarcity: Current situation and Prospects Ing. Ridha Gabouj, Water Expert and former Secretary of State in charge of water resources, MARHP</p> <p>Strategic priorities of the water risk in the mediterranean region Dr. Raoudha Gafrej, Water Expert, Univers de l'Eau, IME</p> <p>Groundwater exploitation in the Anthropocene, Day Zero and scientific pathways to water security for Tunisia Prof. Hakim Gabtni, CERTE, Tunisia</p>	
Group Photo		
16:00 – 16:30	Break	
Parallel Sessions I		
	Room 1	Room 2
16:30 – 18:00	<p>SubS1 : Groundwater management and surface water monitoring and Groundwater Recharge Chairs : Prof. Mlayah & Dr. Jarraya-Horriche</p>	<p>SubS1 : GIS, Remote sensing, and IA applied to water resource Chairs : Prof. Riadh Farah & Prof. Ben Abdallah</p>
18:00-19:00	<p>Room 3</p> <p>Workshop : How to write a Scientific paper ? Prof. Mohamed Ksibi ISBS / Editor-in-Chief Euro-Mediterranean Journal for Environmental Integration (EMJEI)</p>	

SubS1 : Groundwater management and surface water monitoring and Groundwater Recharge

Chairs : Prof. Ammar Mlayah & Dr. Feten Jarraya-Horriche

Venue : Room 1

- 16:30 – 16:45 Fractures analysis in the Takelsa basin (Northeastern Tunisia) using field data and automatic extraction for groundwater investigation
Sabra Dhouioui
- 16:45 – 17:00 Recharge Mapping and water availability analysis for the Zaghoun Karst aquifer (Northeastern Tunisia)
Fairouz Slama
- 17:00 – 17:15 Groundwater recharge estimation for Mornag aquifer using SWB code
Nesrine Ghouili
- 17:15 – 17:30 Precise delimitation of the 'SASS' reservoirs (Southern Tunisia). Well logging contributions
Rafika Ben Lasmar
- 17:30 – 17:45 Hydrochemical and geophysical study of the spatial extent of marine intrusion in the Oualidia coastal aquifer, Morocco
Sadik Youssef
- 17:45 – 18:00 Analyzing the Hydrodynamic Patterns of Zaghoun's Karst Springs: A Comparative Evaluation of ANN Models Using Historical Data
Emna Gargouri-Ellouze

SubS1 : GIS, Remote sensing, and IA applied to water resource

Chairs: Prof. Imed Riadh Farah & Prof. Siham Ben Abdallah

Venue : Room 2

- 16:30 – 16:45 Big Data and Deep Learning for Water Loss Detection Using Multiple Sensors
Yassine Gacha
- 16:45 – 17:00 Enhancing Satellite and Aerial Images: Advances in Spatial and Spectral Super Resolution Techniques
Mohamed Aymen Ben Khalifa
- 17:00 – 17:15 Digital Twins for Africa: Exploring Foundational Concepts, Modern Technologies Integration, Application Landscape, Development Challenges, and Strategies
Mohamed Chahine Bouaziz
- 17:15 – 17:30 Mapping of storage sites for olive mill wastewaters: A combined approach using AHP and machine learning
Bilel Soussi
- 17:30 – 17:45 Advancements in Lithological Mapping: A Review of Machine Learning Algorithms and Remote Sensing Data
Ilyes Salhi
- 17:45 – 18:00 Big geospatial data in favour of smart and sustainable cities :Use case: Real-Time Road Monitoring and Accident Detection Platform for Smart Cities
Hazem Ben Abderrahmen

Day 2 : Saturday, November 9 th , 2024				
8:30 – 12:00	Registration of Participants			
Plenary Lectures <p style="text-align: right;">Moderator :Prof. Ammar Mlayah, CERTE Venue : Room 1</p>				
8:30 – 9:30	Contaminants risks assessment for a safe expansion of reclaimed wastewater reuse and paths for mitigation Prof. Serge Chiron, IRD, France Raman Spectroscopy for environmental analysis and monitoring Prof. Jean-Francois Bardeau, CNRS, France			
Parallel Session II				
	Room 1	Room 2	Room 3	Room 4
9:30 – 11:00	SubS1 : Geological modeling for Resources exploration Chairs : Prof. Chihi & Dr. Jrad	SubS1 : Pollutant control and Water quality assessment Chairs : Prof. Bardeau & Dr. Ben Mabrouk	GGN Event (I) 1 st Geosciences and Environment Interdisciplinary Meetings	SAFE Event (I) Bridging the gap between science and society Chairs : Dr. Khadhar & Ing. Ammar
11:00 – 11:30	Break			
Parallel Session III				
	Room 1	Room 2	Room 3	Room 4
11:30 – 13:00	Climate change and water Chairs : Dr. Sallemi & Dr. Chargui	Treasure Network Event REUSE opportunities through Treasure Chair : Prof. Harmand	GGN Event (II) 1 st Geosciences and Environment Interdisciplinary Meetings	SAFE Event (II) Bridging the gap between science and society Chairs : Dr. Khadhar & Dr. Chkirbene
13:00 – 14:00	Lunch			

Day 2 : Saturday, November 9th, 2024

Scientific Program / Parallel Sessions II

SubS1 : Geological modeling for Resources exploration

Chairs : Prof. Hayet Chihi & Dr. Abir Jrad

Venue : Room 1

Geological modeling and conceptual thinking

- 9:30 – 9:45 3D Geological modeling of multilayered Aquifer Systems
Mohamed Amin Hammami
- 9:45 – 10:00 Comparative Hydrogeological Assessment of Late Cretaceous and Early Eocene Carbonate Aquifers in the Mateur-Hedil region
Sourour El Gattoussi
- 10:00 – 10:15 Geodynamic Study and Petroleum Interest of the Lower Cretaceous in the EL Kef Region (NW Tunisia)
Mohamed Hassen Jebabli

Georesources Characterization and Geophysical Analysis

- 10:15 – 10:30 Advancing Mineral Resource Characterization through Geomodeling and Gravimetry
Selim Braham
- 10:30 – 10:45 Gravity analysis of the Northeastern Atlas of Tunisia
Nouri Ons
- 10:45 – 11:00 Decoding the Soliman Coastal subsurface geometry structure (Tunisia, Mediterranean area): Gravity VS Seismic Data Analysis
Sana Ayari

SubS1 : Pollutant control and Water quality assessment

Chairs: Prof. Jean-Francois Bardeau & Dr. Kawther Ben Mabrouk

Water Pollution Monitoring

- 9:30 – 9:45 Monitoring, evaluation and improvement of tap water quality
Emna Melliti
- 9:45 – 10:00 Assessment of Microplastics in Tap Water: Insights from the Ben Arous Governorate, Tunisia
Tesnim Ben Mbarek
- 10:00 – 10:15 Emerging Contaminants in Surface Waters of the Monastir Coast: Implications for Aquatic Ecosystems and Human Health
Nouha Khiari

Soil contamination (sources and effects)

- 10:15 – 10:30 CO₂ Emissions from Soils Fertilized with Arable Crop Wastes Pre-treated by Anaerobic Digestion and Pyrolysis
Zeineb Louati
- 10:30 – 10:45 Effect of sewage sludge and municipal solid waste biochars on the physicochemical and biological properties of a sandy soil
Amani Haddouk
- 10:45 – 11:00 Sediment Contamination Patterns in Tabarka's Coastal Ecosystem, Northwestern Tunisia: An Integrative Analysis of Trace Metals and Nutrient Loading Dynamics
Maissa Naouar

CONFERENCE PROGRAM DAY 2

GGN Event (I) : 1st Geosciences and Environment Interdisciplinary Meetings 1st Session : GIS, Remote sensing, and IA for Geosciences (CNCT)

Chairs : Pr. Ahmed Siala & Dr. Thouraya Sahli

Venue: Room 3

- | | |
|---------------|---|
| 9:30 – 9:40 | Les contrats programmes de recherche au CNCT: Etat et perspectives
Thouraya Sahli |
| 9:40 – 10:00 | The Smart City project
Haythem Smail |
| 10:00 – 10:20 | The REMINT project
Ahmed Ezzine |
| 10:20 – 10:40 | The Sol project
Hosni Trabelsi |
| 10:40 – 11:00 | Projet REMINT
Wafa Talhaoui |

SAFE Event (I) : Bridging the gap between science and society

Chairs : Dr. Samia Khadhar & Ing. Ali Ammar

Venue: Room 4

- | | |
|---------------|--|
| 9:30 – 10:00 | Water resources in Cap Bon: diagnostic, challenges and needs for research support
Ali Ammar, CRDA Nabeul |
| 10:00 – 10:30 | Advancing Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR) through agreements: key insights from the AGREEMAR project implementation in Cap Bon, NE Tunisia
Anis Chkirbene, INAT |
| 10:30 – 11:00 | Impact of Irrigation with Treated Wastewater on Agricultural Soils: Challenges and Perspectives
Nouha Khiari, CERTE |

Day 2 : Saturday, November 9th, 2024

Scientific Program / Parallel Sessions III

Climate Change and Water

Chairs : Dr. Haykel Sallemi & Dr. Sameh Chargui & Dr. Samira Melki

Venue : Room 1

- 11:30 – 11:45 Time propagation from meteorological to hydrological drought
Majdi Chargui
- 11:45 – 12:00 Hydrological and meteorological drought characterization in Lebna and Oued el Bey Basins, Cap Bon, Tunisia
Malek Drissi
- 12:00 – 12:15 Comparison of High-Resolution Satellite Precipitation Products and a Reanalysis in a Semi-Arid Region
Ines Gharnouki
- 12:15 – 12:30 Impact of Land Use Change on the Hydrological Response: Two Cases Study in Tunisia
Sihem Ben Abdallah
- 12:30 – 12:45 Projections of cereal production in Tunisia under climate change
Firas Tibaoui
- 12:45 – 13:00 COMSOL Multiphysics Model Applied to Simulate Soil Water and Salt Content in the El Haouareb Irrigated Area - Central Tunisia
Emna Abdennour
- 13:00 – 13:15 Impact of climate change on areas vulnerable to water erosion (case of the boulaïraf watershed, Morocco)
Houda Ousbouane Bakioui & Jamal Naoura

Treasure Network Event : REUSE opportunities through Treasure

Chairs : Prof. Jérôme Harmand

Venue : Room 2

- 11:30 – 11:45 The Euromed TREASURE research network and its extensions
Jérôme Harmand
- 11:45 – 12:00 UNESCO Chair project DEF - Waste, Water, Energy
Nihel Ben Amar
- 12:00 – 12:15 On some Anaerobic Digestion models: Mathematical Approaches, and Applications
Nahla Abdellatif
- 12:15 – 12:30 Model-Based Optimization of Fertirrigation with Treated Wastewater for Sustainable Agriculture
Nesrine Kalboussi
- 12:30 – 12:45 Modeling and parameter identification of bioprocesses in bioreactors
Radhouane Fekih-Salem
- 12:45 – 13:00 Modelisation and optimal control of membrane filtration system
Fatma Ellouze

GGN Event (II) : 1st Geosciences and Environment Interdisciplinary Meetings 2nd session : Geosciences Projects

Chairs : Pr. Noamen Rebai & Pr. Olfa Hentati

Venue: Room 3

- | | |
|---------------|--|
| 11:30 – 11:50 | Overview of the Horizon Europe Programme: Focus on Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA)
Mohamed Kefi |
| 11:50 – 12:15 | A Decade of the Euro-Mediterranean Journal for Environmental Integration (EMJEI): Achievements, Stability, and Future Horizons
Mohamed Ksibi |
| 12:15 – 12:30 | Geographical information system of soil resources in Tunisia (SIGREST 2020-2023)
Amal Matoussi |
| 12:30 – 12:45 | SmartSDGTunisia: Leveraging AI and Machine Learning for Sustainable Development and Environmental Monitoring in Tunisia
Hanen Balti |
| 12:45 – 13:00 | Presentation of an Innovative Project: Soil Health and Agriculture Resilience through an Integrated Geographical information systems of Mediterranean Drylands (SHARInG-MeD)
Asma Yahyaoui |

SAFE Event (II) : Bridging the gap between science and society

Chairs : Dr. Samia Khadhar & Dr. Anis Chkirbene

Venue: Room 4

- | | |
|---------------|---|
| 11:30 – 12:00 | Towards a sustainable groundwater resources management in Grombalia region (Cap Bon) through hydrogeological modeling
Jalel Rebhi & Ali Taabouri, CRDA Nabeul |
| 12:00 – 12:30 | Characterization of anthropogenic impacts in Mediterranean intermittent rivers with chemical, ecological and hydrological indicators
Samia Khadhar, CERTE |
| 12:30 – 13:00 | AGREEMed: Innovative Aquifers Governance for Resilient Water Management and Sustainable Ecosystems in Stressed Mediterranean Agricultural Areas
Khawla Masmoudi Jabri |

Day 2 : Saturday, November 9th, 2024

Scientific Program / Parallel Sessions IV

Parallel Sessions IV			
Time	Room 1	Room 2	Room 3
14:00 – 15:45	SubS2 : Geological modeling for resources exploration Chairs : Prof. Boughdiri & Dr. Mzali	Water treatment and reuse of non-conventional water Chairs : Dr. Srarfi & Dr. Khadhar	GGN Event (III) 1 st Geosciences and Environment Interdisciplinary Meetings
15:45 – 16:15	Break + Poster viewing		
	Room 1	Room 2	Room 3
16:15 – 18:00	Poster Contest/Lighting talk		GGN Event (IV) 1 st Geosciences and Environment Interdisciplinary Meetings
	Chairs : Dr. Khadhar Dr. Lachaal and Dr. Kalboussi "GR, WTR,PC, Geo"	Chairs : Prof Rebai, Dr. Azaiez and Cln Smail. "GRS, CC, HH, GEIM"	

Scientific Program / Parallel Sessions IV

SubS2 : Geological modeling for resources exploration Chairs : Prof. Mabrouk Boughdiri & Dr. Housseem Mzali	Venue : Room 1
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Stratigraphy, Biozonation, and Geodynamics

- 14:00 – 14:15 Mathematical modeling of Upper Tithonian Calpionellids (Protozoa, incertae sedis): the genus *Crassicollaria* as a key marker for updated stratigraphy and phyletic reconstructions
Ichrak Cherif
- 14:15 – 14:30 Updated biozonation and correlations of Upper Barremian-Middle Albian successions from NE Tunisia (Zaghouan area): regional geodynamic implications
Abdallah El Khazri

Environmental and Soil Impact Studies

- 14:30 – 14:45 Sedimentological assessment of the Water Table Vulnerability to Pollution by Olive Oil Mill Wastewater, Oued Laya, Sousse area, Eastern Tunisia
Mouna Frigui
- 14:45 – 15:00 Modeling Soil Water Retention in Plastic Clays under Cyclic Wetting and Drying
Samia Rafraf
- 15:00 – 15:15 Storage of phosphogypsum in clayey soils: geotechnical and mechanical impact
Ines Benaoun

Geological Applications and Conservation

- 15:15 – 15:30 Characterization and assessment of stone deterioration on Antonin's baths ruins in CARTHAGE
Aroua Mannai
- 15:30 – 15:45 Use of Tunisian Clay and Spent Bleaching Earth in the Manufacture of Lightweight Aggregates
Amira Cherif

Scientific Program / Parallel Sessions IV

Water Treatment and Reuse of Non-conventional Water

Chairs : Dr. Feyda Srarfi & Dr. Samia Khadhar

Venue: Room 2

- | | |
|---------------|---|
| 14:00 – 14:15 | Synthetic and textile wastewater based cationic dye treatment using local iron tailing waste
Oumaima Grine |
| 14:15 – 14:30 | Phosphate sludge-metakaolin foamed geopolymers and their application in dye removal
Oumaima Karoui |
| 14:30 – 14:45 | Green synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles using Albizia procera leaf extract: Degradation of methylene blue dye via Advanced Oxidation Process and Box–Behnken Design
Hajer Chemingui |
| 14:45 – 15:00 | Enhanced Water Reuse for Irrigation: Synergy of Macrophytes and AOP in Urban Wastewater Treatment
Feriel Araibi |
| 15:00 – 15:15 | Enhanced Photocatalytic Degradation Activity of Amido Black Dye by Electrodeposition of BiVO ₄ nanostructures on TiO ₂ nanotubes
Kawther Ben Mabrouk |
| 15:15 – 15:30 | Exploring microplastics in wastewater reuse for irrigation
Amal Ayari |
| 15:30 – 15:45 | Electrochemical treatment of the actual waste from the industrial landfills of Lindane
Najia Hamrouni |

GGN Event (III) : 1st Geosciences and Environment Interdisciplinary Meetings
3rd Session: Renewable Energy and Climate change

Chairs : Pr. Abdelaziz Mridekh & Dr. Ghaleb Ennine

Venue: Room 3

- 14:00 – 14:25 Latest countries energy transition statistics, and the case of Tunisia
Mongi Marzoug
- 14:25 – 14:45 Exploring Tunisia's Deep Geology: Unveiling the Hidden Potential for Natural Hydrogen
Hakim Gabtni
- 14:45 – 15:00 Advanced Utilization of High-Resolution Aerial Imagery and GAN-Based Super-Resolution Techniques for Solar Deployment Analysis in Tunisia
Mourad El Koundi
- 15:00 – 15:15 The Democratic Republic of Congo's strategic metals in the face of climate change
François Onya Shongo
- 15:15 – 15:30 Intelligent Optimization of Photovoltaic Solar Panel Placement for Enhanced Energy Efficiency
Fares Zaalouni
- 15:30 – 15:45 General discussion

GGN Event (IV) : 1st Geosciences and Environment Interdisciplinary Meetings
4th Session: Water Security and agriculture

Chairs : Pr. Taoufik Hermassi & Dr. Ahmed Ezzine

Venue: Room 3

- 16:15 – 16:45 The OSS Geoportals
OSS team
- 16:45 – 17:00 Modelling and Mapping of water erosion hazard using EO-data and geospatial techniques: Case of Medjerda Watershed
Ahmed Ezzine
- 17:00 – 17:15 Modelling flood risks due to climate change in Bousselem
Saida ben alaya
- 17:15 – 17:30 Integrated Assessment of Phosphogypsum Contamination and Its Environmental Consequences in the Gabes Coastal Ecosystem
Abir Jrad
- 17:30 – 17:45 The Role of Geospatial Data in the Disaster Cycle: A Focus on Hydro-Hazards within the UN-Spider Framework
Wafa Talhaoui
- 17:45 – 18:00 Development of an Advanced System for Monitoring Cereal Crop Campaigns in Tunisia Using Remote Sensing Technologies
Arij Ahmed

Groundwater Management and Surface Water Monitoring and Groundwater Recharge

- GR-Po-01** Hydrogeophysical study of the relationship between the Sfax and Regueb aquifers in the Tunisian Sahel (Mediterranean arid region)
Mohamed Lemine Babou
- GR-Po-02** Geophysical Characterization of Karst Aquifers in a Semi-Arid Environment: A Case Study of the El Houdh Basin (Northwestern Tunisia)
Mohamed Hamrouni
- GR-Po-03** Modelling Dam - aquifer exchanges under climate change: Impact of Dam construction on groundwater recharge of Lebna plain downstream (Cap Bon, Tunisia)
Mohamed Neji
- GR-Po-04** Mapping regional discontinuities and identification of their role in underground fluid flow in reservoir: case study of the of Sidi Jdidi region (North-Eastern Tunisia)
Yosri Khadhraoui
- GR-Po-05** Deep structure of the Mesozoic series in Southern Tunisia. Hydrogeological Implications
Rafika Ben Lasmar
- GR-Po-06** Integrated Hydrogeological and Geophysical Approaches for Characterizing the Sahel Aquifer System
Nermine Ghazouani
- GR-Po-07** Reconstitution of the geometry of the Mio-Plio-Quaternary aquifer system in the Sousse region
Sahar Ben Skander

Water Treatment and Reuse of Non-Conventional Water

- WTR-Po-01** The use of central composite design (CCD) to optimize the coagulation-flocculation process: Application in jar test and industrial scale
Takwa Lazher
- WTR-Po-02** Etiological survey on contaminations of thermal waters and disinfectant tests and purely natural flavorings
Mohamed Ali Dridi
- WTR-Po-03** Reduction of total dissolved solids in industrial water storage tanks while maximizing water resource recovery through reverse osmosis
Aicha Lamali
- WTR-Po-04** Impact of Wastewater Irrigation on Antioxidant Levels in Tomato Plants (Var. BOBCAT) Grown in Oued Souhil, Nabeul
Wided Ben Ammar
- WTR-Po-05** Impact of Wastewater Irrigation on Tomato Plants (Var. BOBCAT) Productivity, Water Content, and Certain Primary Metabolite Production
Sarah Ben Hassine
- WTR-Po-06** Development of eco-friendly biochar from agricultural residues for the removal of Bisphenol A
Hajer Ennouri
- WTR-Po-07** Investigating substrates to enhance constructed wetland performance for wastewater treatment
Marwa Ben Saad

Pollutant Control and Water Quality Assessment

- PC-Po-01** Anthropogenic impacts on a wetland within the Tunis Gulf; wadi Méliane estuary: identification and investigation
Raja Chairi
- PC-Po-02** Calcined phosphate sludges and metakaolin for alkali-activated geopolymers
Walid Hajjaji
- PC-Po-03** Impact of urbanization on the Tazarka lagoon: sedimentological and geochemical characterization
Abir Marzougui
- PC-Po-04** The effect of some chemical parameters of drinking water in the municipality of Qasr Al-Akhyar- Libya
Dukali Almabruk Abujnah
- PC-Po-05** Tackling Water Security Challenges through Pollution Control: A Unified Framework for Microplastic Extraction and Analysis
Sarra Hechmi
- PC-Po-06** Enhancing Olive Oil composition and Water Conservation: The Impact of Buried Clay Pot Irrigation on the Chétoui Variety in Tunisia
Imen Oueslati
- PC-Po-07** Electrical properties analysis of $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{FeO}_3$ ($0 \leq x \leq 0.5$) solid solutions
Rania Lataoui

Geological Modeling for Resources Exploration

- Geo-Po-01** "ED" method to detect the edges of the subsurface structures in the Enfidha plain (Tunisian Sahel) Hydrogeological implications
Maissa Zouaidi
- Geo-Po-02** Late Cretaceous-Paleocene Ostracods and foraminifera assemblages from the Fguira Salah section (Fahs Region, Northern Tunisia): Biostratigraphy and Palaeogeography
Ahlem Amri
- Geo-Po-03** New insights into the subsurface structure of Mornag plain using geophysical data
Mouna Ouerfelli
- Geo-Po-04** Geological and geophysical applied for prospecting the surface and subsurface structure in the Ghar el Melh region (North of Tunisia): Investigations for Prospecting Potential Deep Groundwater Resources
Sofien Alyahyaoui
- Geo-Po-05** Dynamic modeling in the El Borma Field: Petroleum Implications
Mohamed Hassen Jebabli
- Geo-Po-06** Events associated with Cretaceous-Paleocene transition in North Africa (Tunisia, Algeria, Morocco and Libya). Synsedimentary and tectonic record; evidence of a margin activity
Ahlem Amri

GIS, Remote Sensing, and IA applied to water resource

- GRS-Po-01** Soil salinization investigation in the Mejerda lower valley by remote sensing (El Habibia - Mansoura land) Tunisia
Feyda Srarfi
- GRS-Po-02** Groundwater human health risks assessment using GIS technique: A case study of Mornag aquifer
Omeyma Gasmî
- GRS-Po-03** Analysis of Land Cover Changes and Stream Network Evolution in Chaffar Region (Eastern Tunisia) Using High-Resolution Remote Sensing Data
Rouaida Trabelsi
- GRS-Po-04** Hydrology modeling of El Bey Wadi: A Case Study in Tunisia
Farah Khezami
- GRS-Po-05** Extraction of geological lineaments using convolutional neural networks in the Hairech Massif
Sonia Gannouni
- GRS-Po-06** Advanced machine learning techniques for modelling reservoir management with irregular data
Bilal Lefoula
- GRS-Po-07** Geospatial Insights into Carthage's Defensive Strategies: Unveiling Visibility Patterns in Northeastern Tunisia
Oumaima EL Ghali

Climate Change and Water

- CC-Po-01** Changes in Extreme events in a semi-arid context: Drought and Annual Maximum Daily Rainfall over the past decades (Merguellil basin)
Sameh Chargui

Hydro-Hazards and Early Warning System

- HH-Po-01** Development of the white plan of the district hospital of Bousalem; governorate of Jendouba – Tunisia: year 2022
Faten Khemaissia

1st Geosciences and Environment Interdisciplinary Meetings

- GEIM-Po-01** ARIMA algorithm and WCM to retrieve soil moisture based on Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 images over a semi-arid region
Raja Inoubli
- GEIM-Po-02** Spectral-spatial Gabor feature-based deep multi-view learning for blind hyperspectral image unmixing
Refka Hanachi
- GEIM-Po-03** Assessment of Infiltration Dynamics in Oued El Hema Using Remote Sensing Techniques: Implications for Water Resource Management
Mohamed Dhaoui
- GEIM-Po-04** Agro-Geophysical Study of Olive Groves in the Sned Region: Optimizing Irrigation through Electrical Resistivity Tomography and Electromagnetic Surveys
Mohamed Dhaoui
- GEIM-Po-05** Morphometric Analysis of the Maknassy Plain: Insights into Tectonic Structures and Geological Characteristics
Nesrine Bouguerra
- GEIM-Po-06** Geophysical Characterization for deep structuring mapping and Groundwater Resources in a Semi-Arid Environment (Northeastern, Tunisia)
Oussama Kortas
- GEIM-Po-07** Petrophysical analysis of Miocene reservoirs in the Rharrabj Basin (Northwest Morocco) from borehole log data: Application of principal component analysis (PCA).
Ahlam Bouri

Day 3 : Sunday, November 10th, 2024

8:00 –10:00 Registration of Participants

Keynote Presentations

Moderator: Prof. Hakim Gabtni

Venue : Room 1

8:30 – 9:30

Energy Transition: Nord African Perspectives and Challenges

Prof Abdelaziz Mridekh, Université Ibn Tofail, Morocco

Data and modeling in karst systems: potential application to groundwater management and policy in semi-arid regions (Online)

Prof. Joanna Doummar, American University of Beirut/ IAH, Lebanon

Parallel Sessions V

Time	Room 1	Room 2	Room 3
9 : 30– 11:00	SubS2 : Groundwater management and surface water monitoring and groundwater recharge Chairs : Dr. Slama & Dr. Azaiez	SubS2 : GIS, Remote sensing, and IA applied to water resource Chairs : Prof. Riadh Farah & Dr. El Koundi	SubS2 : Pollutant control and Water quality assessment Chairs : Dr. Ben Amor & Dr. Hajjaji
11:00 – 11:30	Break		

CLOSING CEREMONY

Masters of Ceremony : Dr. Mohamed Dhaoui & Dr. Mourad El Koundi

Venue : Room 1

11:30 – 13:00

Summary of Session from Coordinators

Global Discussion

Poster Awards

- Dr. Samia Khadhar
- Dr. Hajer Azaiez

Closing remarks

- Prof. Ammar Mlayah
- Prof. Hakim Gabtni

CONFERENCE PROGRAM DAY 3

Day 3: Sunday, November 10th, 2024

Scientific Programme / Parallel SessionsV

SubS1 : Groundwater management and surface water monitoring and Groundwater Recharge

Chairs: Dr. Fairouz Slama & Dr. Hajer Azaiez

Venue : Room 1

- | | |
|---------------|--|
| 9:30 – 9:45 | Surface water quality for irrigation and dominant hydrogeochemical mechanisms in a Mediterranean wetland ecosystem, North-East Algeria
Faouzi Zahi |
| 9:45 – 10:00 | Hydrogeological Significance of Mediterranean Geoparks In the Framework of the UNESCO IGCP-730 Project
Badiaa Chulli |
| 10:00 – 10:15 | Multi-tracer and isotopic investigation of seawater intrusion in the Lebna plain (Cap-Bon, Tunisia)
Fethi Lachaal |
| 10:15 – 10:30 | Optimization of the strategy for exploiting underground water resources at the University of Bondoukou site (north-east of Côte d'Ivoire)
Coulibaly Issouf |
| 10:30 – 10:45 | Application of multiple approaches to investigate the hydrochemistry evolution of salt in an arid region, sabkha En Noual, Southern Tunisia
Nesrine Nasri |
| 10:45 – 11:00 | Modeling Approach to Groundwater Processes and Pollution: A Hydrogeochemical Assessment of the Grombalia Aquifer in Northeast Tunisia
Farah Khezami |

SubS2 : GIS, Remote sensing, and IA applied to water resource

Chairs : Prof. Imed Riadh Farah & Dr. Mourad El Koundi

Venue: Room 2

- | | |
|---------------|---|
| 9:30 – 9:45 | A Machine Learning-Enhanced SWAT Model for Dynamic Assessment of Natural Groundwater Recharge
Khaoula Khemiri |
| 9:45 – 10:00 | Applying Machine Learning Techniques with Earth Observation Data to Forecast Groundwater Levels: A Case Study of the Lower Medjerda Valley (Tunisia)
Khouloud Neili |
| 10:00 – 10:15 | Geospatial Technologies for Monitoring Water Resources in Supporting life
Osward Mwakifumbwa |
| 10:15 – 10:30 | Spatialization and mapping of water erosion hazard based on multi-decisional AHP approach: case of Medjerda watershed in the North of Tunisia
Dhouha Ben Othman |
| 10:30 – 10:45 | Flood susceptibility mapping using machine learning models: case of the Wadi El Bey Watershed, North-eastern Tunisia
Intissar Barhoumi |
| 10:45 – 11:00 | Groundwater & LCLU monitoring of the Aousja-Ghar El Melh Coastal Aquifer, Gulf of Tunis, Tunisia, Mediterranean
Nadia Khazri |

SubS2 : Pollutant control and Water quality assessment

Chairs:Dr. Tayssir Ben Amor & Dr. Walid Hajjaji

Venue: Room 3

- 9:30 – 9:45 Anthropogenic effects and contamination of Gabes Gulf coastline: geochemical and numerical approaches
Adel Kharroubi
- 9:45 – 10:00 Extent of anthropogenic influence on surface water quality in the wadi Nil watershed (northeastern Algeria): an integrated assessment based on selected characteristic indices
Abdelmalek Drouiche
- 10:00 – 10:15 Assessment of water quality status using heavy metal pollution indices :A case study from Sidi Driss mine, (North West of Tunisia)
Nesrine Ouchir
- 10:15 – 10:30 Conductometric study of struvite prenucleation stage
Sami Ben Moussa
- 10:30 – 10:45 Long-term evolution of water quality and interactions with climate change: Case of the Bab Louta (Taza, Morocco)
Abdelaziz Zouhir& Jamal Naoura
- 10:45 – 11:00 Assessment of Aquifer Pollution Risk Incorporating Characterization of Vadose and Saturated Zones in Mareth, Southern Tunisia
Mounir Atoui

Mr Ridha GABOUJ

Water Expert

Former Secretary of State in charge of water resources, MARHP, Tunisia

Biography: Gabouj Ridha is a water management expert who graduated from AgroParisTech and has dedicated his career to the water sector within the Ministry of Agriculture, Hydraulic Resources, and Fisheries (MARHP). From February 2023 to August 2024, he served as Secretary of State for Water Resources after leading the Water Program. His career includes key roles such as General Director of the General Directorate of Rural Engineering and Water Exploitation and Director of Drinking Water.

Mr. Gabouj has played a crucial role in developing legislation and policies for the water sector, implementing reforms to enhance governance while addressing various challenges, including climate change. He has coordinated significant infrastructure projects in drinking water supply, sanitation, and irrigation, linked to value chain development, and funded by various donors such as the World Bank, KfW, AfDB, JICA, AFD, and others.

He has represented the Tunisian government in numerous international forums and official committees dealing with water and agriculture. Additionally, he has organized international events, including the 5th Mediterranean Water Forum in Tunis, and is an active member of several associations promoting water and environmental conservation.

AGIC5

5th Atlas Georesources International Congress
Hammamet, Tunisia, November 8-10, 2024

Dr. Raoudha Gafrej,
Water Expert, L'Univers de l'EAU
Tunisia

Biography: Dr Ing. Raoudha GAFREJ is a hydraulic engineer graduated from the National Engineering School of Tunis (1988), PhD in Earth Sciences graduated from the Pierre and Marie Curie University Paris VI (1993), specialized in Environmental economics graduated from the Federal Polytechnic School of Lausanne (2006) and in Leadership of public policies, graduate of South Mediterranean University (2019). Dr Gafrej is an international expert in the field of integrated water resources management and adaptation to climate change and a certified trainer in these fields. She was for 18 years a university lecturer and researcher at the University of Tunis El Manar. She participated in the development of various national and regional strategies in the field of water, the green economy, the adaptation of agriculture and ecosystems to climate change, and sustainable development. As a certified trainer, Ms. Gafrej has trained more than 1,500 directors and executives in water, climate change adaptation and other areas. Ms. Gafrej is author and contributor of different publications of World Bank Giz, International Alert, etc. : "Adaptation to a Changing Climate in the Arab Countries" , "Water governance in issues in the media and brings a real advocacy for a sustainable management of water resources under climate change threads.

Prof. Hakim Gabtni,
General Director
Water Research and Technologies
Center CERTE,
Tunisia

Biography: Professor Hakim Gabtni is a senior geoscientist and full professor at the Georesources Laboratory, currently serving as the General Director of the Centre of Water Research and Technologies (CERTE) in Tunisia. He holds a B.S. degree in geology/geophysics (2000), a master's degree (2002), a Ph.D. (2006), and an HDR (2012), all from Tunis El Manar University.

Professor Gabtni specializes in geophysical methods for understanding sedimentary basins and complex geological formations. His work addresses critical areas like groundwater, water resources, energy, geological hydrogen, georesources, and environmental sustainability. His research focuses on gravity and aeromagnetic investigations, three-dimensional seismic modeling, Deep Electromagnetic survey, and near-surface geophysical techniques, including microgravity, seismic refraction/MASW, and electrical resistivity tomography.

With an extensive background in research, development programs, and consulting, Professor Gabtni is also an active editor, reviewer, and author, contributing numerous publications to international scientific journals.

Prof. Serge CHIRON
IRD, France

Biography: Serge Chiron is a senior scientist at IRD. He has more than 25 years of experience in environmental chemistry with a particular focus on emerging contaminants. Their analysis and transformation in the environment as well as their remediation at source by applying nature-based solutions are his main research skills. He has been partner in several national and international projects including two projects funded by PRIMA.

Contaminants risks assessment for a safe expansion of reclaimed wastewater reuse and paths for mitigation
Serge CHIRON, IRD France

Escalating food demands driven by population growth have intensified agricultural practices, placing extraordinary strain on natural resources. The Food and Agriculture Organization predicts a 70% surge in food demand by 2050, paralleling a projected population increase of over 30%. Consequently, strengthening our food systems is becoming essential. Addressing this challenge requires a paradigm shift towards circular economy principles, in which waste becomes a valuable resource. Wastewater emerges as a promising alternative water source for agriculture, provided its characteristics are suitably enhanced. While this approach offers many benefits, this is not without potential risks to human and environmental health that largely stem from the presence of contaminants in the recycled resources (e.g., organic micropollutants, pathogens, antibiotic resistant genes). In this context, different issues and solutions will be discussed including i) contaminants monitoring strategy, ii) regulation and policy as well as iii) water management practices to allow for a safe resource reuse in an effective and replicable way. If needed, contaminants risks must also be mitigated. In rural area, where the capacity of wastewater collection facilities are often underdeveloped, decentralized treatment systems should be prioritized.

Prof. Jean-François BARDEAU
Director of Research
CNRS, France

Biography: Jean-François BARDEAU, Director of Research at CNRS, obtained his PhD in Materials Science at the University of Le Mans in 1997. He specialized in the study of the structural and dynamic properties of different classes of materials such as organic-inorganic hybrid compounds, biomaterials and functional surfaces to focus more recently on the phenomena of electromagnetic exaltation induced on multi-nanostructured metallic surfaces to develop SERS (surface enhanced Raman scattering) sensors. Member of the office of the French Group of Vibrational Spectroscopies (GFSV) since 2015, he is the author of more than 150 publications, 5 patents and has received several distinctions for his work. In march 2024, Jean-François BARDEAU became the new director of the ICMN laboratory (Interfaces, Confinement, Materials and Nanostructures) which is a Mixed Research Unit (UMR n°7374) of the University of Orléans and the French National Center for Scientific Research (CNRS).

Raman Spectroscopy for environmental analysis and monitoring

Jean François Bardeau^{1*},

P. Taugeron¹, M. Rahmani¹, Ludovic Douillard²

¹*Institut des Molécules et Matériaux du Mans – CNRS UMR 6283, Univ. Le Mans, Le Mans, France*

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**Jean-Francois.Bardeau@cnrs.fr*

Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS) is an exceptionally powerful and non-invasive optical technique, increasingly used for the detection and identification of trace-level molecular analytes. Despite its immense potential, one of the key obstacles to the widespread quantitative application of SERS lies in the reproducible fabrication of substrates that exhibit consistent, high enhancement factors. These factors are intimately linked to the formation on the surface of "hot spots", regions of intense electromagnetic field enhancement. In response to this challenge, we successfully developed an efficient and inexpensive approach for fabricating metallic SERS substrates through thermal evaporation. In our recent work, we developed a bilayer gold substrate based on a primary layer approximately 100 nm thick, overlaid with an additional evaporated gold layer. During the deposition process, the metal clusters gradually coalesce, initially forming irregular nanoscale structures with small asperities before merging into a continuous film. This controlled evolution allows for fine-tuning of the interparticle spacing, creating an extended percolation network — ideal conditions for the generation of abundant hot spots.

However, a critical question remains: how does the surface quality of the primary layer influence the spatial distribution and density of hot spots, and consequently, the overall SERS enhancement factor of the substrate? To address this, we conducted numerical simulations, creating model surfaces and by using the Finite Element Method (COMSOL Multiphysics®), we mapped the distribution of hot spots, elucidating thus the influence of the base layer's topographical irregularities on the substrate's plasmonic behavior. Our findings were further validated by experimental results obtained using PhotoEmission Electron Microscopy (PEEM), which confirmed the critical influence of the primary gold layer's morphology on the plasmonic properties and overall SERS performance.

Our optimized nanorough Au substrates enabled the detection of crystal violet (CV), a chemical dye and antifungal agent classified as a biohazard and potent carcinogen, at a concentration of $5 \cdot 10^{-9}$ M, highlighting the potential of such substrates for applications in environmental monitoring.

Prof. Abdelaziz MRIDEKH
Ibn Tofail university,
Faculty of sciences,
Natural resources and
Sustainable laboratory
Maroc

Biography: Abdelaziz Mridekh is a professor of Applied Geophysics at Ibn tofail university, "Géosciences des ressources naturelle". He is head of research unit "Géophysique et hydrosystèmes". He earned his DEA in 1994 (at the university of Tunis El Manar) and Doctorat national at Ibn Tofail University in 2002. He worked for 3 years in water exploration for GéoAtlas, one of leader in hydrogeophysics in Africa. He specializes in hydrogeophysics and petroleum basin exploration, sequence and seismic stratigraphy, wire-line logging and GIS. He is currently conducting many research programs, consulting and is the author of several international publications and a reviewer in international journals.

Energy Transition: Nord African Perspectives and Challenges

Abdelaziz MRIDEKH^a

Rachidi Samir^b, Nouhail Nabil^b, Achraf Essalih^c, Ibtihal El Aichouni^a

- a) *Ibn Tofail university, Faculty of sciences, Natural ressources and Sustainable laboratory*
- b) *Institut de recherche en energie solaire et energies nouvelles*
- c) *Société Marocaine de Stockage Souterrain*

The energy transition is a crucial issue of the 21st century, driven by the need to reduce carbon emissions and promote sustainable energy sources. Globally, this transition significantly influences the economy, redefining investments and energy policies. In Africa, the energy transition presents considerable opportunities for sustainable development but also faces unique challenges, such as limited access to technology and financing.

Morocco possesses significant fossil energy potential, with production zones in the Gharb region and numerous offshore projects. These resources offer an opportunity to balance the energy mix while transitioning towards more sustainable sources. In parallel, Morocco stands out as a regional leader in adopting renewable energies, with ambitious initiatives like the Noor solar complex in Ouarzazate, one of the largest in the world. The country has implemented an energy strategy aiming to increase the share of renewables to 52% of its energy mix by 2030. Additionally, Morocco is actively developing its green hydrogen policy, recognizing its potential to decarbonize industry and transport.

In this context, Morocco is exploring underground storage sites, with ongoing projects like MELHY, which aim to enhance energy security and stability by addressing the intermittency challenges of renewable energies. This underground storage presents numerous technical challenges, requiring the integration of diverse scientific disciplines such as geomechanics, geophysics, and reservoir modeling to ensure effective and safe implementation.

We examine the role of the energy transition in the global economy and its impact in Africa, emphasizing the importance of an energy mix tailored to the specificities of each country. In conclusion, it highlights the necessity of a personalized and collaborative approach to ensure a successful energy transition, beneficial for both Africa and the rest of the world.

Prof. Joanna Doummar
American University of Beirut
IAH Vice President MENA
Lebanon

Biography: Joanna Doummar is the Chair of the Department of Earth Sciences and an associate professor of groundwater hydrology at the American University of Beirut. Joanna's research focuses on water quality and quantity assessments in Mediterranean, semi-arid, and snow governed karst and fractured aquifers. Her research projects include the high-resolution monitoring and collection of time series data, subsurface characterization, and development of numerical groundwater flow. This approach is essential to drive, using science-supported evidence, policy and infrastructural interventions for GW protection and sustainability on pilot scale.

She has supervised many undergraduate and graduate students in research topics in hydrogeology that culminated in various publications. She is the Vice president (MENA Region) of the International Association of Hydrogeologists and an elected member of the IAH Karst Commission. She has been also been elected in the World Economic Forum Young Scientists Community- Class of 2020."

Data and modeling in karst systems: potential application to groundwater management and policy in semi-arid regions

Prof. Joanna DOUMMAR

American University of Beirut
IAH Vice President MENA
Lebanon

The presentation will present work undertaken in an experimental poorly studied semi-arid region in Lebanon: the Nahr El Kalb surface water/ aquifer system composed of limestone and dolostones of Jurassic to Cenomanian age. A high-resolution monitoring is taking place since 2014 to characterize the subsurface, understand spring responses, conceptualize flow and transport in complex systems, and simulate flow in variably heterogeneous systems of Mount-Lebanon. Different methods have been applied for the characterization of flow and transport in different types of karst systems with variable heterogeneities, hydrodynamic conditions, and climatic input: 1) snow-governed versus rain governed springs, 2) fissured karst aquifers, 3) highly complex heterogenous karst with little knowledge of the subsurface, and 4) highly complex karst with a cave access. Such utilized methods include times series analysis, tracer experiments, micropollutants sampling campaigns, stable isotope studies etc.

The presentation will present briefly selected models such as distributed integrated hydrological, lumped linear reservoir, 2-D dual continuum, discrete fractured network models, and recently machine learning applications that have been tailored to simulate flow in the investigated spring catchments to account for the degree of karstification and varying hydrodynamic responses.

In sum, the talk will illustrate a long-term methodology that allows to assess water quality and quantity in Lebanon in particular. This approach can be upscaled to the region for a better sustainable karst groundwater management, testing of alternative methods for enhanced recharge, and policy development and implementation in poorly studied catchment areas.

AGIC5

8-10 November 2024

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